

Synthesis of some Mixed Ligand Mono(xanthato) Complexes of Chromium and Study of their Infrared Spectra

B. B. NATH* and S. P. BHATTACHARYA

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan-731 235

Manuscript received 26 August 1991, accepted 23 September 1991

Mixed ligand complexes having the composition $K_2[Cr(ox)_2L].xH_2O$ where ox is the oxalato group, L the bidentate uninegative alkyl isoalkyl or aryl xanthato group and x the number of water of crystallisation, have been synthesised. In the present study, potassium salts of methyl-, ethyl-, n-propyl-, iso propyl-, n-butyl-, iso butyl-, sec-butyl- and benzyl xanthates have been used to generate L. The infrared spectral studies of these mixed ligand chromium complexes viz potassium bis(oxalato)alkyl/aryldithiocarbonato(xanthato)chromate(III) along with the corresponding ligand potassium xanthates have been undertaken. The contribution of different canonical structure towards the C=O and C=S stretching frequencies of the complexes are examined. The effects of chain length structural variations on the different mode of vibrations are discussed.

CHELATING agents like alkyl/aryldithiocarbonates (xanthates) produce four-membered ring with metal ions. The ligands are very similar to N-alkyl, N,N-dialkyl dithiocarbamates. Both of them are uninegative bidentate chelating agents with two sulphur as donor atoms having similar bite angles. However, the infrared spectra of the complexes aroused considerable interest after the observation of Chatt *et al.*¹ that xanthato complexes do not absorb in the C=O region (structure 1b) whereas dithiocarbamates display strong band corresponding to C=N bond. They observed that out of the three canonical structures of the ligands,

one of the structure, 1b do not contribute to the total structure in the xanthato complexes. Watt and McCormick² however did not rule out the contribution of the structure 1b. Furthermore, there have been certain differences with regard to the assignment of C=S, C-O-C and C-O frequencies. For example, Little *et al.*³ assigned C=S frequencies at 1 020-1 070 cm^{-1} and C-O-C frequencies at 1 200 and 1 110-1 140 cm^{-1} whereas Shankaranarayana and Patel⁴ assigned C=S and C-O frequencies at 1 200-1 260 and 1 010-1 037 cm^{-1} respectively. Keeping the above facts in mind, we prepared a series of mixed ligand complexes of chromium in which one of the ligands is xanthato

group and studied infrared spectra in a wide region. In these mixed ligand complexes reported by us, we systematically varied the R-group of the xanthate in order to examine the nature of the absorbing groups as well as to find out the nature of contribution of the structure 1b to the overall structure of the complex.

Experimental

The parent complex *cis*- $K[Cr(ox)_2(H_2O)_2].2H_2O$ (abbreviated as PC) was prepared by standard method⁵ and its composition checked⁶. The potassium salts $K[SSCOR]$ of the different xanthates (henceforth [SSCOR] group termed as L) were prepared following the reported procedure⁶ with necessary modifications. Each compound was recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) and the purity was checked by analysing the sulphur content gravimetrically⁷. The respective complex $K_2[Cr(ox)_2L].xH_2O$ was prepared by mixing PC with $K[L]$ in 1 : 1 proportion (by weight) in fixed amount of water so that the final strength of the prepared complex be 0.25 molal. The whole mixture was shaken well and equilibrated for 0.5 h at 45° in a constant temperature bath. The solution was then slowly evaporated at room temperature. The dark green crystals thus obtained were repeatedly washed with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) in which the xanthates dissolved readily whereas the complexes remained insoluble. The product was filtered and the resulting shining dark-green crystals were preserved in vacuum desiccator over silica gel. The complexes thus prepared, were fully characterised and reported elsewhere⁸. Here we report our findings on the infrared spectra of these compounds. Table 1 lists the analytical, magnetic and a few electronic spectral data of these complexes. Figure 1 presents

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC AND ELECTRONIC (MULL) SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found (Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M.	λ_{max} nm
	Oxalate	Cr	S		
$\text{K}_2[\text{Cr}(\text{ox})_2\text{SSCOCH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5].3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	37.81 (37.66)	10.96 (11.12)	13.18 (13.69)	4.39	410,565,690
$\text{K}_2[\text{Cr}(\text{ox})_2\text{SSCOC}_2\text{H}_5].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	38.08 (37.98)	11.11 (11.22)	13.29 (13.80)	4.34	410,565,690
$\text{K}_2[\text{Cr}(\text{ox})_2\text{SSCO}n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	37.10 (36.86)	10.89 (10.89)	13.09 (13.40)	4.31	410,565,690
$\text{K}_2[\text{Cr}(\text{ox})_2\text{SSCO}i\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	37.00 (36.86)	10.71 (10.89)	13.11 (13.40)	4.23	410,565,690
$\text{K}_2[\text{Cr}(\text{ox})_2\text{SSCO}n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	35.99 (35.81)	10.49 (10.57)	12.25 (13.02)	4.36	410,565,690
$\text{K}_2[\text{Cr}(\text{ox})_2\text{SSCO}i\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	36.02 (35.81)	10.72 (10.57)	12.12 (13.02)	4.32	410,565,690
$\text{K}_2[\text{Cr}(\text{ox})_2\text{SSCO}sec\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	36.10 (35.81)	10.60 (10.57)	12.16 (13.02)	4.36	410,565,690
$\text{K}_2[\text{Cr}(\text{ox})_2\text{SSCOCH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5].\text{H}_2\text{O}$	34.89 (34.68)	10.09 (10.24)	12.34 (12.61)	4.35	410,565,690

the infrared spectrum respectively of (A) PC, (B) one representative xanthate ligand and (C) corresponding complex; while Fig. 2 presents the spectrum at low frequency region.

Results and Discussion

The IR spectra of the mixed ligand complexes show many overlapping bands. Each compound (a representative spectrum, that of potassium bis(oxalato)ethylxanthatochromate(III), dihydrate is given in Fig. 1) show broad band at 3 000–3 500 cm^{-1} due to lattice water, caused by antisymmetric and symmetric OH stretchings. Along with

Fig. 1. Infrared spectrum of (A) *cis*- $\text{K}[\text{Cr}(\text{ox})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, (B) potassium ethylxanthate, (C) potassium bis(oxalato)ethylxanthatochromate(III).

the broad water band, a small but significant peak at 3 500 cm^{-1} indicative of free OH stretching of the coordinated water is present in the PC (Fig. 1) but not in the resulting complexes. In the 1 600–1 700 cm^{-1} region, band for HOH bending merges with $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ band for oxalate and several peaks in the spectra could be observed in this region. Between 2 800 and 3 000 cm^{-1} region, the ligand, $\text{K}[\text{L}]$ show peaks, indicative of the C–H stretchings^{2,9}. The nature of the band and the number of peaks are dependent on the structure of R (Fig. 1). In the benzyl ligand, however, these peaks are observed between 2 900 and 3 100 cm^{-1} . In the resulting

complexes the symmetry of the ligand molecules are changed. The peaks of the ligand band are separated widely to give three weak bands mainly at $\sim 2\,900$ (CH_3), $\sim 2\,800$ (CH_2) and $\sim 2\,500$ cm^{-1} (C–H). The band at 2 900 cm^{-1} is due to ν_{CH_3} , since the other two bands are absent in the methyl complex.

All the complexes give a conspicuous strong band at 1 400 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-C}}$ of the oxalato group¹⁴, as well as a combination band of two other weak bands, present in each of the ligands: one slightly above 1 400 cm^{-1} due to the presence of $-\text{CH}_2-$ group, and the other at slightly lower than 1 400 cm^{-1} due to the terminal $-\text{CH}_3$ group of the hydrocarbon chain¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

The complexes absorb either at 1 255 or at 1 260 cm^{-1} and each of them gives a strong band. Such a band is also present in the PC. Little *et al.*³ also observed that xanthato chelates of metals as well as dixanthogens give strong band around 1 250 cm^{-1} , and concluded that this intense band is due primarily to a C–O vibration of the C–O–C linkage in xanthate complexes. Several other workers agreed to this assignment. Kruger and Winter¹¹ and Mohammad *et al.*¹² observed that this band is shifted to lower frequency on adduct formation and concluded that the canonical form (1b) has smaller contribution in the base adducts as compared to the base free complexes. In the ligand, $\text{K}[\text{L}]$, this band is weak or practically absent. Thus the replacement of S^-K^+ ionic bond of the ligand by S–Cr σ -bonding and ring formation in the resulting coordination compounds influence normal mode of vibration, especially $\nu_{\text{O-C}}$ and $\nu_{\text{R-O-C-S}}$ of the ligand to a great extent.

The xanthate ligands are characterised by a number of strong bands at 1 000–1 200 cm^{-1} (Fig. 1B) involving O–C and C–S bonds^{2,3,12}, the former giving several peaks around 1 120 cm^{-1} and the latter around 1 000 cm^{-1} . In the resulting complexes, some of these peaks merge resulting two strong bands. The strong band at $\sim 1\,000$ cm^{-1} is due to delocalisation of π -bonds, whereby the two C=S and C–S bonds are made nearly equivalent in the resulting complexes. Furthermore, different canonical structures of the ligand (1b–3b) contribute to the several strong bands around 1 100

to 1160 cm^{-1} whereas in the complexes having the ring structure,

there is extensive electron delocalisation. The RO-group is weakly electron-releasing and in the reported complexes the extent to which the metal-sulphur σ -bonds are effective in drawing off electrons from the sulphur atoms to promote a drift of electrons from oxygen to sulphur is not very high. In the resulting complexes the frequency is lowered only to the extent of $10\text{--}20\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which indicates that structure **1b** of the canonical forms does contribute, but not in a very significant way. Our findings are in conformity with those of Watt and McCormick² and Chatt *et al.*¹.

In the free ligands, the O-C bond order slightly varies with the nature of electron-repelling group R, e.g. methyl-xanthate absorbs at 950 cm^{-1} , ethyl-xanthate at 940 cm^{-1} , n-propyl-xanthate at 930 cm^{-1} and n-butyl-xanthate at 920 cm^{-1} . The difference in contribution is, however, not very high but is significant. In the resulting complexes, a sharp band is observed at 900 cm^{-1} . This is of course the combination band since the PC absorbs also at 900 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_s(\text{CO}) + \delta(\text{O}-\text{C}=\text{O})$.

All the complexes display a strong band at $\sim 810\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\delta(\text{O}-\text{C}=\text{O}) + \nu(\text{MO})$; none of the ligands possesses this band. There is a shift of 10 cm^{-1} in the complexes, since PC gives this band at 820 cm^{-1} . Each of the complexes as well as PC display a strong band at $\sim 550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu_{\text{MO}} + \nu_{\text{CC}}$ of the oxalato group¹⁴. The ligands K[L], and the corresponding complexes present the peak at 410 cm^{-1} which coincides with the band indicative of $\nu(\text{MO}) + \text{ring deformation of the oxalato}$

Fig. 2. Infrared spectrum of potassium bis(oxalato)-ethylxanthatochromate(III) at low frequency region, with that of potassium ethyl xanthate (dotted line in the background).

group (Fig. 1). In PC this band is at 420 cm^{-1} . Chromium-sulphur σ -bond presents the peaks at 335 and 360 cm^{-1} (Fig. 2). Other workers^{2,12} also observed absorption due to the vibration of metal-sulphur bond in this region, with their respective metal-xanthato complexes.

From the above discussion it is evident that the position of the specific ir bands are almost fixed in all the reported complexes and indicates that C-S and C-O motions are highly coupled in the complex ion which may be represented by the resonance structure (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Resonance structure of the complex bis(oxalato)-alkyl/aryldithiocarbonatochromate(III).

Acknowledgement

Support of this work by the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, as well as partial financial support for research by Visva-Bharati is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. J. CHATT, L. A. DUNCANSON and L. M. VENZA, *Suomen Kemistilehti*, **89**, 75.
2. G. W. WATT and B. J. McCORMICK, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1965, **21**, 753.
3. L. H. LITTLE, G. W. POLING and J. LEJJA, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1961, **39**, 754.
4. M. L. SHANKARANARAYANA and C. C. PATEL, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1961, **39**, 1633.
5. W. G. PALMER "Experimental Inorganic Chemistry", Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1965, p. 387.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 4th ed., ELBS, London, 1978, p. 588.
7. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., ELBS, London, 1962, p. 467.
8. S. P. BHATTACHARYA and B. B. NATH, unpublished work.
9. R. S. DRAGO, "Physical Methods in Inorganic Chemistry", Affiliated East-West Press, New Delhi, 1968, p. 219.
10. A. T. CASEY and J. R. THACKERAY, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1972, **25**, 2085.
11. A. G. KRUGER and G. WINTER, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1971, **24**, 161.
12. T. J. MOHAMMED, J. A. MUSTAFA and S. E. AL-MUKHTAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 725.

13. D. COUCOUVANIS and J. P. FACKLER, Jr., *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 2047.
14. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 4th. ed., Wiley, New York, 1986, p. 245.
15. S. A. FRANCIS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1951, **19**, 942.
16. N. SHIFFARD, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1955, **51**, 1485.
17. N. B. COLTHUP, L. H. DALY and S. E. WIBBERLY, "Introduction to Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy", 2nd. ed., Academic, New York, 1975, p. 395.